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Foreign Language Teachers' Attitudes and Motivation Towards Distance Learning

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Abstract

Language is an important tool of communication, especially in a foreign setting. Foreign language teachers, help their students to access foreign experiences by reason of their ability to communicate with foreign nationals. Teachers' motivation however influences foreign language education and its effectiveness. The aim of this study is to examine the predictive effect of foreign language teachers' motivations on their attitudes towards distance education. For this purpose, 356 foreign language teachers who teach in Turkey (240 females, 116 males) were reached. The ages of the teachers are in the range of 23-64 and the mean is 41.9 (SD =9.44). Personal Information Form, Attitude Scale Toward Distance Learning (ASTDL), and Academic Motivation Scale (AMS) were applied to the participating teachers. Multiple regression was used to analyze the data in the study. Accordingly, extrinsic motivation predicts both positive and negative attitudes towards distance education. In addition, motivation predicts a positive attitude.

Keywords: Distance Learning, Attitude, Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation, Amotivation

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

Traditional face-to-face training became unavailable in the last months of 2019 due to the outbreak of COVID-19. Teachers and students who could not go to schools due to Covid-19 started to do their lessons via distance education. Although the students born after 2000, known as Generation Z, also referred to as the internet generation formed the majority, however, were they ready for distance education? Perhaps the most important question is how ready the teachers (trainers) were. In other words, teachers' attitudes towards distance education, their knowledge / skills / abilities to use distance learning tools, their rate of transferring their knowledge to students, their teaching motivation (Sauro & Chapelle, 2017) will determine the success of this type of education. Studies have shown that a teacher's competence positively affects teachers' participation in professional learning activities and increases the quality of teaching (Goddard et al., 2000; Özdamlı, et al., 2009; Thoonen et al., 2011; Tschannen-

moran & Woolfolk, 2001). The inevitability of distance learning with the Covid-19 pandemic has forced teachers into distance education.

The P21 foundation summarizes the skills expected from students as the first quarter of the 21st century is almost complete. This can be seen in Figure 1. These skills, which are called 21st century skills, are under almost all headings of foreign language learning (3R), communication (4C) and effective use of technology. P21 includes key subjects (3Rs: English, reading and language arts, world languages, arts, mathematics, economics, science, geography, history, government, and civic knowledge). It consists of three main skill areas referred to as ‘career skills’, ‘learning and innovation skills’, ‘knowledge, media and technology skills’ (Kyllonen, 2012; P21, 2019; Trilling & Fadel, 2009).

Figure 1: 21st century skills

Source: P21 (2019)

Communication skills can be defined as expressing thoughts and ideas by using verbal (Korkut Owen & Demirbaş Çelik, 2018), written and non-verbal communication skills effectively in various forms and contexts, being an active listener and communicating effectively in different environments (including multilingual) (P21, 2019; Trilling & Fadel, 2009). It is believed that one of the subjects that contribute to the practice in the development of these skills is foreign language teachers. The use of distance learning in foreign language teaching dates back to the 1980s. One of the first examples of this is that the National British Program in England in the 1980s taught French via radio and television (Clifford, 1990). U.S. Congress, Office of Technology Assessment (1989) found that language learning through distance learning is as successful as face-to-face language learning (U.S. Congress, 1989). Since those days, there have been many technological developments. These developments positively affected all stages of language learning. For example, with the developments in the field of telecommunications, the communication between the teacher and the learner, the learner and the learner has provided the opportunity to be done very quickly in written, oral and visual forms. Likewise, both web 2.0 applications and artificial intelligence-based applications (such as Duolingo) give very good results for the writing, reading and listening stages (Al-Johali, 2019; Otto, 2017; Yavuz et al., 2020).

1.2 Distance Learning

Distance learning is defined as the learning method where the teacher and the learner are in different places and communication is provided by technological tools (Atabek, 2020; Keegan, 1996). Today, although the definition of distance learning remains basically the same, it can be done in different ways. According to the definition made by the University of Wisconsin Continuing Education Group, “*Distance learning is designed to provide student interaction and learning certification; It is a planned learning / teaching experience that uses a wide range of technologies to reach a distant audience*”. The most important reason for this definition change is the developments in the field of educational technologies. Distance learning has removed all borders and walls in education. In other words, distance learning provides the opportunity to learn at the desired age, place and time, at the desired speed, using the desired environment. Features such as distance, time, place, age, socio-economic

status, physical disability keep distance education and lifelong learning are always on the agenda (Algharaibeh, 2020; Riga et al., 2020).

Attitude is defined as the intensity of the positive or negative emotion about a psychological object (Ajzen, 2005; Petty & Krosnick, 2014; Pratkanis, 2014; Thurstone, 1931). According to Thurstone (1931), attitude treats objects only in terms of an evaluation (affirmative-negative or preferred-not preferred) (Ajzen, 2005). For this reason, it is important to determine the positive and negative attitude when examining the attitude towards distance education. However, according to the definition accepted by social psychologists in recent years, attitude brings integrity and consistency to the individual's thoughts, feelings and behaviours towards an object (Albarracín & Shavitt, 2018; Bohnet & Dickel, 2011; Tavşancıl, 2018). From this point of view, distance learning is considered by Çelik & Uzunboylu (2022) as four sub-dimensions under the positive and negative upper dimensions of the attitude towards distance education. The positive attitude dimension consists of the usefulness of distance learning as an educational tool and the preference of distance education. Negative attitude consists of sub-dimensions of communication deficiencies in distance learning and preferring face-to-face training (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Attitude toward distance learning

Source: Çelik and Uzunboylu (2022)

If individuals (teachers) have a positive attitude towards distance education, they adopt distance learning as a useful tool and want to teach with distance learning (Çelik, 2021). Teachers' positive attitudes towards teaching bring them closer to education (Johnson & Howell, 2005). According to Büssing et al. (2019), attitude towards teaching increases the desire to teach. Similarly, it is thought that positive attitude towards distance learning will increase teachers' desire to teach and thus their success (Illarionova et al., 2021). However, teachers with a negative attitude tend to prefer the education environments they are accustomed to and know, that is, face-to-face education. The most important arguments for this will be their belief that they cannot provide social presence in distance education. That is, they will explain the negative attitude with the lack of social presence (Rahimi et al., 2020; Sutiah et al., 2020). Some of the physical factors that will negatively affect teachers' attitudes towards distance learning can be listed as follows: the absence of additional payments for the number of students in the classroom and the time spent, the inability to receive visual feedback from students, concerns about the quality of the content, insufficient training and resources, increased workload, lack of online teaching experience and change in teachers' traditional roles (Güler & Özkan, 2018; Lloyd et al., 2012).

Distance learning seems to be an indispensable method during and after the pandemic process which is defined as the new normal. In order to increase the effectiveness of distance education, teachers need to make extra effort to learn the intricacies of technology and develop their enthusiasm and passion for teaching (Yehya, 2020). In order for this effort to be made and to maintain its continuity, teachers need this driving force called motivation. When the teacher's motivation is noticed by the students, the students' interest, desire and enthusiasm for learning increases (Mishra, 2020). Regardless of the learning and teaching environment, motivated behaviour is positively influenced by motivational factors (Maehr & Braskamp, 1986; Salehi & Abdi, 2019; Thoonen et al., 2011).

1.3 Motivation

According to Self Determination Theory (SDT), people are born with an innate instinct to act (Ryan & Deci, 2000a). However, it is not always possible for people to act with intrinsic motivation (Algharaibeh, 2020). Therefore, the motivation that drives a person can arise not only from one's internal resources but also from external sources (Manchanda, 2017). The motivation that occurs due to an extrinsic reason in SDT is called

extrinsic motivation. At this point, it is important to regulate and internalize extrinsic motivation. SDT has developed a comprehensive motivational model for this process (Ryan & Deci, 2000b).

Lee (2000) stated that many factors affect motivation. These factors are lesson design, the level of interaction and facilitating student motivation, and the fact that the teacher and learner are in separate spaces negatively affects motivation, and collaborative environments should be provided to prevent this. Computer use anxiety caused by the lack of sufficient computer experience and skills also causes a decrease in motivation (Ekizoglu & Ozcinar, 2010; Elci & Kuloglu, 2019; Elsayed & Salama, 2020; Lee, 2000).

The source of motivation in the teaching-learning process varies (Ryan & Deci, 2000a; Urea, 2018). As with students, teachers also need to be motivated to be effective in distance education. If the desire to teach emerges with the teacher's own will and effort, if the motivation is based on an internal reward, the source of motivation comes from outside (Balaban-Salı, 2004). In addition, sometimes there may be a lack of motivation. There are many dynamics that are integrated in the person who loves his profession. It can be said that one of its main dynamics is motivation (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2012). Once a person understands the components of the structure of motivation, he or she can be better motivated and stay motivated (Weiner, 2013). In a comparative study with distance learning students and students taking courses on campus, distance learning students showed higher intrinsic motivation (Wighting et al., 2008). Based on this, it is thought that the intrinsic motivation of distance learning teachers will also be high. Teachers who are intrinsically motivated can use many different strategies and perform better academically (Tavoosy & Jelveh, 2019; Ünal-Karagüven, 2012). When the teacher remains motivated and enjoys the teaching profession, students do not only learn the content the teacher teaches, but students are also motivated to learn (Czubaj, 1996).

1.4 Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the predictive effect of foreign language teachers' motivations on their attitudes towards distance education. In order to achieve these aims, the authors have sought to answer the following questions:

1. Is Distance learning attitude and motivation associated with foreign language teachers?
2. Does motivation in foreign language teachers predict attitude towards distance education?

2. Method

2.1 Participants

Three hundred and fifty-six (356) volunteers participated in this study as foreign language teachers from Turkey. Two hundred and forty (240) representing 67.4% of the participants are female and 116 (32.5%) are male. The ages of the teachers are in the range of 23-64 and the mean is 41.9 (SD = 9.44). The working time of the teachers participating in the study varies between 1-40 year, with an average of 16.9 (SD = 9.28). In terms of branches, 221 (57.6%) are English teachers, 53 (13.8%) are German teachers, 48 (12.5%) are Arabic teachers, 46 (12%) are French teachers and 16 (4.2%) other (Russian, Chinese, Japanese etc.).

2.2 Measures

2.2.1 Personal Information Form (PIF)

The participants were asked questions regarding gender, age, professional experience and which language they teach.

2.2.2 Attitude Scale Toward Distance Learning (ASTDL)

The attitude scale towards distance learning was developed by Çelik & Uzunboylu (2022) to determine how individuals perceive distance education. The scale is 16 items and is graded in a 5-point Likert type. Total score is not obtained from the scale. The dimensions of the scale are scored separately. The scale has four sub-dimensions:

usefulness, lack of social presence, preference to distance learning, and preference to face to face learning. Among these dimensions, usefulness and preference to distance learning constitute the upper dimensions of positive attitude, lack of social presence and preference to face to face learning. According to the reliability study of the scale on university students, the internal consistency coefficients were Cronbach alpha (α) .81 for usefulness, .73 for lack of social presence, .67 for preference for distance learning, and .82 for preference for face-to-face learning.

The two-dimensional (positive attitude and negative attitude) structure of this scale was applied to teachers using the same questions in this study. Goodness of fit values according to CFA performed: [χ^2 (103, N = 356) = 473.04, $p < .01$; GFI = .85; CFI = .78; IFI = .78; SRMR = .084; RMSEA = .097]. The internal consistency coefficients obtained in this study were .83 for positive attitude and .73 for negative attitude, respectively.

2.2.3 Academic Motivation Scale (AMS)

The academic motivation scale was developed by Vallerand et al. (1992). With the scale consisting of 28 items and 7 sub-scales, intrinsic motivation (intrinsic motivation to know, intrinsic motivation to accomplish, and intrinsic motivation to stimulation), extrinsic motivation (external regulation, introjected regulation, and identified regulation) and amotivation can be measured. The subscales in the 7-point Likert scale are scored separately. Scores between 7-28 can be obtained from each subscale and it is understood that the motivation source indicated by the subscale with a higher score is high. In this study, the Turkish version of the scale adapted by Ünal-Karagüven (2012) was used. In addition, the evaluation of the scale can be made according to three dimensions combined (extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation) (Karataş & Erden, 2012). In this adaptation study, the internal reliability coefficient of the extrinsic motivation sub-dimension was .84, the internal reliability coefficient of the extrinsic motivation sub-dimension was .83, and the internal reliability coefficient of the intrinsic motivation sub-dimension was .87. In this study, the internal consistency coefficient was calculated as .87, .89 and .93, respectively.

2.3 Data Analysis

In this study, the data were analyzed with the SPSS 20 program. In the research, the normality assumption was tested first. Accordingly, it was determined that Kolmogorov-Smirnov values of all variables were above .05. Scatter diagrams were checked for the assumption of linearity of the relationship between variables. From the assumptions of the regression analysis, the presence of multicollinearity was investigated by looking at tolerance and variance inflation factor (VIF). As a result of examining the VIF and tolerance values of the dependent variables, it was calculated that the VIF values ranged between 1.03 and 2.60 (the highest = 2.60 <5), and the CI values were between .385 and .973 (the lowest = .385 > .2). In this study, it was determined that VIF and tolerance values fulfil the relevant condition. It is concluded that these values also do not show multiple linear relationships between variables (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2016). Finally, the relationship between variables was examined to determine whether there was a correlation between variables. Multiple regression was used in the analyses.

3. Results

In this study, positive attitude, and negative attitude, which are the dimensions of the ASTDL, are considered as dependent variables. Independent variables are intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and lack of extrinsic motivation. Descriptive statistics of the dependent and independent variables in the study and the correlations between these variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Means, standard deviations (SD) and bivariate correlations among all variables

	Mean	SD	PA	NA	IM	EM	AM
Positive Attitude (PA)	33.11	7.95	—				
Negative Attitude (NA)	20.54	5.11	.218	***	—		
Intrinsic Motivation (IM)	56.50	17.79	.183	***	.298	***	—
Extrinsic Motivation (EM)	58.20	15.92	.275	***	.339	***	.777
						***	—

Amotivation (AM)	9.93	6.59	.241	***	-.026	-.079	.028	—
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Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

According to Table 1 is, the positive attitude towards distance learning and intrinsic motivation is ($r = .218$, $p < .001$), extrinsic motivation ($r = .183$, $p < .001$) and extrinsic motivation ($r = .241$, $p < .001$). There was a low level of positive correlation. A low-level positive correlation was found between negative attitude towards distance learning and intrinsic motivation ($r = .298$, $p < .001$) and extrinsic motivation ($r = .339$, $p < .001$).

Table 2: Regression analysis for Positive Attitude.

	B	SE	β	t	p
Intrinsic Motivation (IM)	-0.00814	0.0361	-0.0182	-0.226	.822
Extrinsic Motivation (EM)	0.14117	0.0402	0.2825	3.512	< .001
Amotivation (AM)	0.27986	0.0612	0.2319	4.570	< .001

Note: Dependent variable is *Positive Attitude (PA)*; predictors are *Intrinsic Motivation (IM)*, *Extrinsic Motivation (EM)* and *Amotivation (AM)*.

According to Table 2, a multiple linear regression was calculated to predict positive attitude based on intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and amotivation. A significant regression equation was found ($F_{(3,347)} = 17.3$, $p < .001$), with an R^2 of .123. Participants' predicted positive attitude is equal to $22.57426 - (-0.00814) IM + 0.14117 EM + 0.27986 AM$, where IM, EM and AM are measured as total score in sub-dimensions. Positive attitude increased -0.00814 points for each point of intrinsic motivation, 0.14117 for each point of extrinsic motivation and 0.27986 for each point of amotivation. Both extrinsic motivation and amotivation were significant predictors of positive attitude.

Table 3: Regression analysis for Negative Attitude.

	B	SE	β	T	p
Internal Motivation (IM)	0.0252	0.0230	0.0877	1.10	0.274
Extrinsic Motivation (EM)	0.0870	0.0257	0.2706	3.38	< 0.001

Note: Dependent variable is *Negative Attitude (NA)*; predictors are *Intrinsic Motivation (IM)*, and *Extrinsic Motivation (EM)*.

According to Table 3, a multiple linear regression was calculated to predict negative attitude based on intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. A significant regression equation was found ($F_{(2,348)} = 23.2$, $p < .001$), with an R^2 of .118. Participants' predicted negative attitude is equal to $14.0581 - 0.0252 IM + 0.0870 EM$, where IM and EM are measured as total scores in sub-dimensions. Negative attitude increased 0.0252 points for each point of intrinsic motivation and 0.0870 for each point of extrinsic motivation. Only extrinsic motivation was a significant predictor of negative attitude.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, the predictive effect of motivation types of foreign language teachers on their positive and negative attitudes towards distance learning was examined. First of all, the relationship between motivation and attitude towards distance learning was considered. Accordingly, it has been determined that positive attitude towards distance learning is intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation correlated. Negative attitude towards distance learning is associated with intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Both external motivation and extrinsic motivation were significant predictors of positive attitude. Only external motivation was a significant predictor of negative attitude.

While positive attitude towards distance learning is associated with all types of motivation, negative attitude is associated with intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The attitude towards distance learning can be considered to contain many elements. For example, teachers are expected to transfer their teaching competencies to technological tools (Akbas et al., 2018; Cullen & Greene, 2011). Thus, both teaching competence (Wang et al.,

2014) and technological literacy competence (Senkbeil & Ihme, 2017) can affect the types of motivation of teachers. Of course, individual differences (Niżegorodcew, 2012; Skehan, 2014) between teachers will also be effective at this point.

Intrinsic motivation is associated with both positive and negative attitudes. This result can be handled in two ways. First, it shows that teachers with high intrinsic motivation are motivated to work under all conditions, that is, the urge to teach continues in distance education environments. On the other hand, teachers who have high intrinsic motivation may want to communicate face to face with their students (Çelik and Uzunboyulu, 2022). They want to apply the teaching methods and techniques they use in traditional education in distance learning. However, in order to provide distance learning, teachers must perform extra efforts. Studies have mostly found that teachers do not have additional preparation and planning time, and they use the activities in their face-to-face lessons in online environments, which affects students and teachers' performance, motivation, interest and participation in the lesson (Apipalakul et al., 2017; Güner et al., 2016). Teachers caught unprepared for distance learning due to the pandemic may have adopted a negative attitude because they think that they cannot use the teaching methods and techniques they use in traditional education in the distance learning environment. Despite all these related factors, it was found that intrinsic motivation did not explain the attitude towards distance education. The reason for this finding may be that distance learning is very new compared to traditional education environments and foreign language teachers have not yet developed an attitude about the effectiveness of these new environments (Kurt & Yavuz, 2018).

Extrinsic motivation is also associated with both positive and negative attitudes. Extrinsic motivation means that the individual is motivated by an external influence (Cardinali & Barbeito, 2018; Ryan & Deci, 2000a). These external effects may be factors such as the obligation to teach, suggestions made by the school administration, and the image of teaching (Ryan & Deci, 2020c). These factors can be associated with a positive attitude towards distance education. As a matter of fact, a study found that mechanisms such as rewards played a role in increasing the motivation of unwilling teachers and thus forming a positive attitude (Dotters-Katz et al., 2016; Mola & Dagnew, 2020). One of the factors determining the extrinsic motivation of the teacher is student interest (Keller et al., 2017). Students interest in distance learning can also increase teachers' motivation. For this, having interactive platforms, at least interactive lessons with the relevant students, can play an active role. Of course, another problem here is the preparation process for the lesson because distance learning may require more preparation than normal education. Because of these factors, teachers may develop negative attitudes. In this context, external motivation was found as significant predictors of positive and negative attitude. Cullen & Greene (2011) also revealed in their study that extrinsic motivation predicts teachers' attitudes in the context of technology integration.

Extrinsic motivation is only associated with positive attitude. At the same time, extrinsic motivation predicts positive attitude towards distance education. If the teacher has no motivation at all, which may have psychological / sociological reasons related to the pandemic process, the teacher may also be unmotivated in his normal life. Teachers who see distance learning as a means of escape from school, who do not want to communicate with students much, and who still try to teach are expected to show a positive attitude.

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